

Identifying context-aware functionalities in practice

Thank you very much for your interest in participating in this survey.

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Context-aware functionalities are functionalities that take context into consideration to produce a certain system behavior, typically an adaptation or recommendation. For example, when YouTube automatically adapts the quality of the video you are watching based on the speed of your network connection, this is context awareness. Or when Instagram recommends a place to tag your new photo based on your location, this is also context awareness. As context information such as time, location, weather, user activity, device characteristics, network status, and countless others are becoming increasingly more accessible, the potential for adding context awareness to our applications is enormous.

Identifying novel, unexpected, and even delightful context-aware functionalities in practice can be challenging, though. What context information is relevant for a given user task? How can context information be combined? What if there is a large number of contextual factors?

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED] This is where we ask for support from you as someone who has (or had) worked on the identification of new context-aware functionalities.

The survey is anonymous and will take about 20 minutes to complete.

All participants will receive the results of this research.

If you have any question, please do not hesitate to contact: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

There are 26 questions in this survey.

PART 1: Usage of context models in practice

How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities?

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	None	Low	Good	High	Expert
My experience with context-aware functionalities is...	<input type="radio"/>				

Help:

Context-aware functionalities are functionalities that take context into consideration to produce a certain system behavior, typically an adaptation or a recommendation, without explicit user interaction. Imagine, for example, a video streaming platform where the user can watch movies, series, documentaries, etc. In this specific application domain, examples of context-aware functionalities could include:

- "When the network connection speed of the user's device is slow, the system shall decrease the quality of the video being streamed."
- "If the user has rated videos of a certain category positively, the system shall recommend other videos of the same category for the user's playlist."
- "When the user is in the living room of their house, and it is evening, and the user has started to stream a movie on their TV, the system shall set the ambient light to 25%."

In your practical experience in the last 5 years, how often have context-aware functionalities been taken into consideration in the software projects in which you have been involved? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Frequently	Always
They have been taken into consideration...	<input type="radio"/>				

Help:

Context-aware functionalities are functionalities that take context into consideration to produce a certain system behavior, typically an adaptation or a recommendation without explicit user interaction. Imagine, for example, a video streaming platform where the user can watch movies, series, documentaries, etc. In this specific application domain, examples of context-aware functionalities could include:

- "When the network connection speed of the user's device is slow, the system shall decrease the quality of the video being streamed."
- "If the user has rated videos of a certain category positively, the system shall recommend other videos of the same category for the user's playlist."
- "When the user is in the living room of their house, and it is evening, and the user has started to stream a movie on their TV, the system shall set the ambient light to 25%."

In your practical experience in the last 5 years, have you used any sort of context model to support the identification of potential context-aware functionalities that can be added to your software projects? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'Never' at question '2 [MODEL1]' (In your practical experience in the last 5 years, how often have context-aware functionalities been taken into consideration in the software projects in which you have been involved? (They have been taken into consideration...)) *and* Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

YES, in my practical experience I have used context models to support the identification of context-aware functionalities.

NO, in my practical experience I have not used context models to support the identification of context-aware functionalities.

Help:

In the previous examples, some **contextual elements** are indicated, for instance "network connection speed", "video quality", "user's ratings", "video category", "user location", "time", and "ambient light (luminosity)". The list of meaningful contextual elements varies from application domain to application domain.

Contextual elements and their respective entities are sometimes organized in a context model. A **context model** is a conceptual model that somehow represents your system's context and can be used to help you identify context-aware functionalities.

There is no standard for representing context models. Types of representation include: plain text, tables, and graphics/diagrams, for example. They also vary in degree of formality.

Since there are different definitions for "context model" in different phases of the software development lifecycle, it is important to emphasize that our definition positions the context model in the early requirements phase and focuses on facilitating the identification of context-aware functionalities.

In your practical experience in the last 5 years, how are context models represented?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'Never' at question '2 [MODEL1]' (In your practical experience in the last 5 years, how often have context-aware functionalities been taken into consideration in the software projects in which you have been involved? (They have been taken into consideration...)) *and* Answer was 'YES, in my practical experience I have used context models to support the identification of context-aware functionalities.' at question '3 [MODEL2]' (In your practical experience in the last 5 years, have you used any sort of context model to support the identification of potential context-aware functionalities that can be added to your software projects?) *and* Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

Please write your answer here:

Help:

A **context model** is a conceptual model that somehow represents your system's context and can be used to help you identify context-aware functionalities.

There is no standard for representing context models. Types of representation include: plain text, tables, and graphics/diagrams, for example. They also vary in degree of formality.

Since there are different definitions for "context model" in different phases of the software development lifecycle, it is important to emphasize that our definition positions the context model in the early requirements phase and focuses on facilitating the identification of context-aware functionalities.

In your practical experience in the last 5 years, how much have you benefited from context models to identify new context-aware functionalities for your software projects? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'Never' at question '2 [MODEL1]' (In your practical experience in the last 5 years, how often have context-aware functionalities been taken into consideration in the software projects in which you have been involved? (They have been taken into consideration...)) and Answer was 'YES, in my practical experience I have used context models to support the identification of context-aware functionalities.' at question '3 [MODEL2]' (In your practical experience in the last 5 years, have you used any sort of context model to support the identification of potential context-aware functionalities that can be added to your software projects?) and Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Not at all	A little	Reasonably	A lot	Extremely
I have benefited from context models...	<input type="radio"/>				

Help:

In the previous examples, some **contextual elements** are indicated, for instance "network connection speed", "video quality", "user's ratings", "video category", "user location", "time", and "ambient light (luminosity)". The list of meaningful contextual elements varies from application domain to application domain.

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There is no standard for representing context models. Types of representation include: plain text, tables, and graphics/diagrams, for example. They also vary in degree of formality.

Since there are different definitions for "context model" in different phases of the software development lifecycle, it is important to emphasize that our definition positions the context model in the early requirements phase and focuses on facilitating the identification of context-aware functionalities.

Please read this introduction to some concepts.

Assume for a moment that you are involved in a software project of a video streaming platform and you want to improve the "search" functionality by making it context-aware in order to provide the user with more insightful search results.

Activities during context modeling include:

1- Identification of contextual elements

"What are the contextual elements that make sense for my video streaming platform?"

Ex.: 🕒 time, 📍 user location, 😊 user mood, 🌤️ weather...

2- Analysis of accessibility of contextual elements

"Can I access/read all identified contextual elements (✓) or it is not feasible in my project to access/read some of them (✗)?"

Ex.: time ✓, user location ✓, user mood ✗, weather ✓ ...

3- Analysis of relevance of contextual elements

"Which contextual elements are relevant for the system-supported user task 'Search for a video'?"

Ex.: 🏆 time (most relevant), 🏆 weather (second most relevant), 🏆 user location, ...

4- Analysis of combinations of contextual elements

"Which combinations of contextual elements are relevant for the system-supported user task 'Search for a video'?"

Ex.: When it is 🌃 night_(time) at 🏠 home_(location) and there is 🌧️ rain_(weather), the user might prefer a certain type of content.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

In your practical experience in the last 5 years, have your context models included information about...

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'Never' at question '2 [MODEL1]' (In your practical experience in the last 5 years, how often have context-aware functionalities been taken into consideration in the software projects in which you have been involved? (They have been taken into consideration...)) and Answer was 'YES, in my practical experience I have used context models to support the identification of context-aware functionalities.' at question '3 [MODEL2]' (In your practical experience in the last 5 years, have you used any sort of context model to support the identification of potential context-aware functionalities that can be added to your software projects?) and Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Frequently	Always
...which contextual elements were identified?	<input type="radio"/>				
...the accessibility of the contextual elements?	<input type="radio"/>				
...which contextual elements are the most relevant ones for specific tasks?	<input type="radio"/>				
...how contextual elements should be combined to support specific tasks?	<input type="radio"/>				

Help:

From the previous example:

1- Identification of contextual elements

"What are the contextual elements that make sense for my video streaming platform?"

Ex.: time, user location, user mood, weather...

2- Analysis of accessibility of contextual elements

"Can I access/read all identified contextual elements ('yes') or it is not feasible in my project to access/read some of them ('no')?"

Ex.: time (yes), user location (yes), user mood (no), weather (yes)...

3- Analysis of relevance of contextual elements

"Which contextual elements are relevant for the task 'Search for a video'?"

Ex.: 1: time (most relevant), 2: weather (second most relevant), 3: user location, ...

4- Analysis of combinations of contextual elements

"Which combinations of contextual elements are relevant for same task?"

Ex.: When it is "night_(time) at home_(location) and there is rain_(weather)", the user might prefer a certain type of content.

In your practical experience in the last 5 years regarding the identification of context-aware functionalities, the context model has served as... *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'Never' at question '2 [MODEL1]' (In your practical experience in the last 5 years, how often have context-aware functionalities been taken into consideration in the software projects in which you have been involved? (They have been taken into consideration...)) *and* Answer was 'YES, in my practical experience I have used context models to support the identification of context-aware functionalities.' at question '3 [MODEL2]' (In your practical experience in the last 5 years, have you used any sort of context model to support the identification of potential context-aware functionalities that can be added to your software projects?) *and* Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Frequently	Always
...input	<input type="radio"/>				
...output	<input type="radio"/>				

Help:

"Input" means that the context model is an artifact that you have before the identification of context-aware functionalities, and which is intended to support you in discovering new context-aware functionalities.

"Output" means that the context model is generated after you have already identified context-aware functionalities and is intended to document what you discovered.

PART 2: Context modeling

How would you rate your experience... *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	None	Low	Good	High	Expert
...in conceptual modeling?	<input type="radio"/>				
...in context modeling?	<input type="radio"/>				

Help:

Context modeling here means the activity of creating context models. A **context model** is a conceptual model that somehow represents your system's context and can be used to help you identify context-aware functionalities.

In your practical experience in the last 5 years, how have context models for discovering context-aware functionalities been created? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'Never' at question '2 [MODEL1]' (In your practical experience in the last 5 years, how often have context-aware functionalities been taken into consideration in the software projects in which you have been involved? (They have been taken into consideration...)) *and* Answer was 'YES, in my practical experience I have used context models to support the identification of context-aware functionalities.' at question '3 [MODEL2]' (In your practical experience in the last 5 years, have you used any sort of context model to support the identification of potential context-aware functionalities that can be added to your software projects?) *and* Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Fully manual	Semi-automated	Fully automated
The creation of context models is...	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Help:

"Fully manual" means that human work is necessary to model the context. Note that if you use software to aid manual work (for example, a CASE tool to draw diagrams), but you still do it yourself, it should be classified as manual work.

"Semi-automated" means that parts of the modeling activities are automated (by means of artificial intelligence or data mining, for example).

"Fully automated" in this context means that the context modeling is completely carried out by software.

In your practical experience in the last 5 years, what has been automated or semi-automated in context modeling?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'Never' at question '2 [MODEL1]' (In your practical experience in the last 5 years, how often have context-aware functionalities been taken into consideration in the software projects in which you have been involved? (They have been taken into consideration...)) and Answer was 'YES, in my practical experience I have used context models to support the identification of context-aware functionalities.' at question '3 [MODEL2]' (In your practical experience in the last 5 years, have you used any sort of context model to support the identification of potential context-aware functionalities that can be added to your software projects?) and Answer was NOT 'Fully manual' at question '10 [MODEL8]' (In your practical experience in the last 5 years, how have context models for discovering context-aware functionalities been created? (The creation of context models is...)) and Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

📌 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Identification of contextual elements
- Analysis of accessibility of contextual elements
- Analysis of relevance of contextual elements
- Analysis of combinations of contextual elements

Other:

Help:

From the previous example:

1- Identification of contextual elements

"What are the contextual elements that make sense for my video streaming platform?"

Ex.: time, user location, user mood, weather...

2- Analysis of accessibility of contextual elements

"Can I access/read all identified contextual elements ('yes') or it is not feasible in my project to access/read some of them ('no')?"

Ex.: time (yes), user location (yes), user mood (no), weather (yes)...

3- Analysis of relevance of contextual elements

"Which contextual elements are relevant for the task 'Search for a video'?"

Ex.: 1: time (most relevant), 2: weather (second most relevant), 3: user location, ...

4- Analysis of combinations of contextual elements

"Which combinations of contextual elements are relevant for same task?"

Ex.: When it is "night_(time) at home_(location) and there is rain_(weather)", the user might prefer a certain type of content.

Do you have experience with the identification of context-aware functionalities where there are several contextual elements? (Consider systems with at least 12 contextual elements) *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'Never' at question '2 [MODEL1]' (In your practical experience in the last 5 years, how often have context-aware functionalities been taken into consideration in the software projects in which you have been involved? (They have been taken into consideration...)) *and* Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes

No

In your opinion, how complex are these activities in systems with several contextual elements? (Consider systems with at least 12 contextual elements) *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Not complex at all	Slightly complex	Reasonably complex	Highly complex	Extremely complex
Identification of contextual elements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Analysis of accessibility of contextual elements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Analysis of relevance of contextual elements for specific tasks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Identification of meaningful combinations of contextual elements for specific tasks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Help:

From the previous example:

1- Identification of contextual elements

"What are the contextual elements that make sense for my video streaming platform?"

Ex.: time, user location, user mood, weather...

2- Analysis of accessibility of contextual elements

"Can I access/read all identified contextual elements ('yes') or it is not feasible in my project to access/read some of them ('no')?"

Ex.: time (yes), user location (yes), user mood (no), weather (yes)...

3- Analysis of relevance of contextual elements

"Which contextual elements are relevant for the task 'Search for a video'?"

Ex.: 1: time (most relevant), 2: weather (second most relevant), 3: user location, ...

4- Analysis of combinations of contextual elements

"Which combinations of contextual elements are relevant for same task?"

Ex.: When it is "night_(time) at home_(location) and there is rain_(weather)", the user might prefer a certain type of content.

In your opinion, does professional experience influence the ability to identify context-aware functionalities in systems with several contextual elements? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Professional experience has no influence at all.
- Professional experience has as much influence as in non-context-aware functionalities.
- Professional experience has more influence in context-aware functionalities than in non-context-aware functionalities.

Help:

"Several contextual elements": consider systems with at least 12 contextual elements.

In your opinion, to which extent is the relevance of contextual elements for specific user tasks analyzed in systems with several contextual elements? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Never	Superficially	Reasonably	In detail	Systematically
The relevance is analyzed...	<input type="radio"/>				

Help:

"Systematically" here means that the analysis of the relevance is aimed at completeness (each individual contextual element is analyzed for each user task).

"Several contextual elements": consider systems with at least 12 contextual elements.

Analysis of relevance of contextual elements:

From the previous example: "Which contextual elements are relevant for the task 'Search for a video'?"

Ex.: 1: time (most relevant), 2: weather (second most relevant), 3: user location, ...

In your opinion, why is the relevance of contextual elements for specific user tasks not analyzed systematically? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'Systematically' at question '15 [MODELING5]' (In your opinion, to which extent is the relevance of contextual elements for specific user tasks analyzed in systems with several contextual elements? (The relevance is analyzed...)) *and* Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

! Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- It is NOT necessary to analyze the relevance of all contextual elements.
- Although necessary, it is too time-consuming.
- Although necessary, it is error-prone.
- Although necessary, it is not always intuitive.

Other:

Help:

Analysis of relevance of contextual elements:

From the previous example: "Which contextual elements are relevant for the task 'Search for a video'?"

Ex.: 1: time (most relevant), 2: weather (second most relevant), 3: user location, ...

In your opinion, why is it not necessary to analyze the relevance of all contextual elements? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was at question '16 [MODELING6]' (In your opinion, why is the relevance of contextual elements for specific user tasks not analyzed systematically?) *and* Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

Please write your answer here:

Help:

Analysis of relevance of contextual elements:

From the previous example: "Which contextual elements are relevant for the task 'Search for a video'?"

Ex.: 1: time (most relevant), 2: weather (second most relevant), 3: user location, ...

In your opinion, to which extent are meaningful combinations of contextual elements for a specific user task analyzed in systems with several contextual elements? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Never	Superficially	Reasonably	In detail	Systematically
Combinations are analyzed...	<input type="radio"/>				

Help:

"Systematically" here means that each possible combination (2x2, 3x3, ..., NxN) is analyzed.

"Several contextual elements": consider systems with at least 12 contextual elements.

Analysis of combinations of contextual elements:

From the previous example: "Which combinations of contextual elements are relevant for the task "Search for a video"?"

Ex.: When it is "night_(time) at home_(location) and there is rain_(weather)", the user might prefer a certain type of content.

In your opinion, why are such combinations not analyzed systematically (aiming at completeness)? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT 'Systematically' at question '18 [MODELING9]' (In your opinion, to which extent are meaningful combinations of contextual elements for a specific user task analyzed in systems with several contextual elements? (Combinations are analyzed...)) *and* Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

! Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- It is NOT necessary to analyze all combinations.
- Although necessary, it is too time-consuming.
- Although necessary, it is error-prone.
- Although necessary, it is not always intuitive.

Other:

Help:

Analysis of combinations of contextual elements:

From the previous example: "Which combinations of contextual elements are relevant for the task "Search for a video"?"

Ex.: When it is "night_(time) at home_(location) and there is rain_(weather)", the user might prefer a certain type of content.

In your opinion, why is it not necessary to analyze all combinations of contextual elements? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was at question '19 [MODELING10]' (In your opinion, why are such combinations not analyzed systematically (aiming at completeness?)) *and* Answer was NOT 'None' at question '1 [CHARMODEL0]' (How would you rate your experience in software projects with context-aware functionalities? (My experience with context-aware functionalities is...))

Please write your answer here:

Help:

Analysis of combinations of contextual elements:

From the previous example: "Which combinations of contextual elements are relevant for the task "Search for a video"?"

Ex.: When it is "night_(time) at home_(location) and there is rain_(weather)", the user might prefer a certain type of content.

FINAL

We are almost done.

Is there anything you would like to share about your experience with identification of context-aware functionalities in practice?

Please write your answer here:

Help:

Context-aware functionalities are functionalities that take context into consideration to produce a certain system behavior, typically an adaptation or a recommendation without explicit user interaction. Imagine, for example, a video streaming platform where the user can watch movies, series, documentaries, etc. In this specific application domain, examples of context-aware functionalities could include:

- "When the network connection speed of the user's device is slow, the system shall decrease the quality of the video being streamed."
- "If the user has rated videos of a certain category positively, the system shall recommend other videos of the same category for the user's playlist."
- "When the user is in the living room of their house, and it is evening, and the user has started to stream a movie on their TV, the system shall set the ambient light to 25%."

In which field is your background? *

! Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

Computer Science (or related fields)

Graphical Design

Mathematics and Statistics

Electrical Engineering

Communication/Advertising

Administration

Other

How many years of experience do you have in the identification/definition of software functionalities? *

! Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

Less than 2 years

2 to 4 years

5 to 9 years

10 years or more

In which types of software projects are you usually involved in? *

! Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

Mobile

Web

Desktop apps

Embedded software

Other:

What is your industry sector? If there is more than one, please choose the most significant one. *

! Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Agrobusiness
- Communications/Electronics
- Construction
- Defense
- Education
- Energy and Natural Resources
- Finance, Insurance, and Real Estate
- Ideological/Single-Issue (e.g. political parties, NGOs, etc.)
- Labor Union
- Lawyers
- Public Sector
- Research
- Software Development
- Transportation
- Entertainment
- Other

What is the size of the company where you work? *

! Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Fewer than 10 employees
- 10 to 49 employees
- 50 to 249 employees
- 250 employees or more

Thank you for your participation!

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.

Identifying context-aware features in practice (LEAVE YOUR EMAIL)

There are 2 questions in this survey.

Thank you for your participation!

Do you want to be notified about the results of this survey? If YES, please provide your email address.

Please write your answer here:

Your email address will NOT be linked to your responses.

Some survey participants will join us in individual follow-up conversations to highlight their viewpoints and find out more about what we are doing. If you are also interested in this and want to get a closer look at this research, please let us know whether we may contact you via e-mail.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT at question '1 [THANKS1]' (Do you want to be notified about the results of this survey? If YES, please provide your email address.)

! Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- No, thanks.
- Yes, I am interested.

Thank you for your participation!

Submit your survey

Thank you for completing this survey.